
**A Model Village Manyachiwadi Of Patan Tehsil Of Satara District,
Maharashtra: A Geographical Study.**

Dr. Sandeep Sampat Tadakhe

*Associate Professor, HOD, Department of Geography,
Balasaheb Desai College, Patan, Thl. Patan, Dist. Satara, MH,
Corresponding Author –Dr. Sandeep Sampat Tadakhe*

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15063389

Abstract:

Manyachiwadi village in Patan tehsil of Satara District in Maharashtra has overcome various challenges and become a self-sufficient community and has achieved success in various areas like solar power, water conservation, agriculture, education, health, and sanitation. The village has also implemented innovative initiatives like vermicomposting, biogas, and e-learning through collective efforts of villagers in Manyachiwadi. Village has become an ideal village through implementing innovative initiatives and collective efforts. Manyachiwadi village is considered an excellent example of rural development not only in Maharashtra but also in the whole of India. The unity and hard work of the villagers have proven that any difficulty can be overcome with the right direction and efforts. Since the establishment of the Gram Panchayat in 2001, the village has received 76 awards, with the first one in 2005. It is a model of sustainable development, with leaders from other villages frequently visiting to replicate its success. Due to all these efforts, village is at the forefront in all matters.

Key Words: Manyachiwadi, Recycled Materials, Environmental Friendly.

Introduction:

Manyachiwadi, a village nestled along the banks of the Wang River in the Maladn village of Patan tehsil of Satara district. Since the establishment of the Gram Panchayat in 2001, the village has received 76 awards, with the first one in 2005. It is a model of sustainable development, with leaders from other villages frequently visiting to replicate its success. The village has effectively implemented environmental friendly programs such as waste management, proper drainage, and a consistent water supply. Numerous artworks made from recycled materials like tires, dishes, and plastic items can be seen throughout the village. With the collective efforts of the villagers and approach to energy conservation and solar power transformed Manyachiwadi into a solar-

powered village, earning it the distinction of being the first solar village in Maharashtra. Located at the foothills of the Sahyadri mountain range of Patan tehsil in western Maharashtra, Manyachiwadi is a picturesque village that has gained recognition not only for its natural beauty but also for the remarkable achievements of its residents. A symbol of rural Maharashtra's traditional way of life, Manyachiwadi has overcome numerous challenges; including water scarcity, low agricultural productivity, and limited access to education. Through collective efforts, Manyachiwadi village has become an ideal village through collective efforts. The village has overcome various challenges and become a self-sufficient community. It has achieved success in areas like solar power, water conservation, agriculture, education, health, and sanitation.

The village has also implemented innovative initiatives like vermicomposting, biogas, and e-learning.

Objectives of the research:

1. To study the socio-economic improvements of Manyachiwadi village of Patan tehsil.
2. To study the various environmental friendly changes in Manyachiwadi village of Patan tehsil.

Study Region:

Fig. 1. Study Region

The Manyachiwadi village Patan tehsil is located at 17°25'79" latitude and 73°98'03" longitude and 610 meters and above main sea level in Patan tehsil of Satara district in Maharashtra, India. It is situated 27 km away from sub-district headquarter Patan. The total geographical area of village is 110.82 hectares. The average temperature within the range of 25°C to 30°C with hotter summers and milder winters and the average annual rainfall is around 1631.16 mm. Manyachiwadi has a total population of 420 peoples, out of which male population is 189 while female population is 231. Literacy rate of Manyachiwadi village is 75.71% out of which 85.71% males and 67.53% females are literate. Working population is 33.5 %. There are about 107 houses in Manyachiwadi village.

Research Hypotheses:

Manyachiwadi village had many problems in the beginning and has undergone complete development and now at the forefront in all respects.

Research Methodology:

While selecting the sample for the research, 100 respondents were selected using the purposive sampling method in the non-probability selection method. For the present research, the *Sarpanch*, *Deputy Sarpanch*, *Gram Sevak*, Women's Self-Help Group President, Secretary and Members as well as the local people of the village have been selected according to simple random sampling method to select the sample for the research. To analyze the information and data, averages, tables, percentages, graphs, etc. Statistical techniques have been used.

Data Sources:

The present research is mainly based on primary sources. While collecting data and information, information has been obtained from *Sarpanch*, *Deputy Sarpanch*, *Gram Sevak*, Women's Self-Help Group President, Secretary and Members as well as the local people of the village through questionnaires, interviews and observations. The secondary data were collected from various reference books, District Rural Development Agency reports, various websites, newspapers, etc.

Discussion and Result:

Manyachiwadi village has made its identity as an ideal village due to its collective efforts. Due to the hard work and struggle of the villagers, this village has today emerged as a strong and self-reliant society. Due to all these efforts, Manyachiwadi village is considered an excellent example of rural development not only in Maharashtra but also in the whole of India. The unity and hard work of the villagers have proven that any difficulty can be overcome with the right direction and

efforts. Manyachiwadi has overcome numerous challenges; including water scarcity, low agricultural productivity, and limited access to education. Through collective efforts, Manyachiwadi village has become an ideal village through collective efforts. The village has overcome various challenges and become a self-sufficient community. It has achieved success in areas like solar power, water conservation, agriculture, education, health, and sanitation. The village has also implemented innovative initiatives like vermicomposting, biogas, and e-learning.

Water Conservation and Harvesting:

One of the primary concerns in Manyachiwadi was the scarcity of water. To address this issue, the villagers implemented various water conservation and harvesting measures. These included the construction of check dams, water harvesting structures, and the adoption of water-saving techniques. As a result, the village witnessed a significant reduction in water scarcity, and agricultural productivity increased. Today, the village boasts of a reliable 24/7 water supply, thanks to the efficient use of rainwater harvesting and water conservation methods. Until recently, Manyachiwadi faced severe water scarcity. A water purifier near the panchayat office provides 5 liters of purified drinking water for just ₹1, allowing families to fill their containers and take them home. 98 respondents have responded on water conservation and agricultural improvement. 98% of the people feel that work has been done in this regard.

Agriculture and Economic Progress:

Following the successful water conservation efforts, the farmers of Manyachiwadi adopted modern farming techniques. The village focused on increasing production through organic farming and diverse cropping patterns. This led to an increase in the farmers' income and

an improvement in the village's economic condition. 95 respondents have responded on agriculture and economic development. 95% of the people feel that work has been done in this regard.

Solar Project and Waste Management:

The concept of getting light in every house in the village using natural energy has been realized in every house in this village. Solar energy power supply systems have been installed in every house in the village. This has resulted in a saving of about 60 to 70 percent in household bills. This has helped the citizens of the village save on their electricity bills. Through this, Manyachiwadi has become the first solar village in the state. Manyachiwadi's solar project is nearing completion. The village successfully lobbied for a special government rule change to accommodate the project, building on their existing excellent work in other environmental areas. Residents participating in the solar energy program pay approximately ₹9,000 and receive a ₹30,000 subsidy, making solar energy a financially viable option. This initiative brings the village close to becoming independent from the Maharashtra State Electricity Board (MSEB). The village school, gram panchayat office, anganwadi, and local dairy all run on solar energy, making them a true model of renewable energy. Notably, the gram panchayat office also has a free charging station for electric two-wheelers, encouraging the use of clean energy for transportation. 100 respondents have responded on solar projects and waste management. 100% of the people feel that work has been done in this regard.

Manyachiwadi's waste management is exemplary. The village is clean, with separate bins for plastic and minimal plastic use. The women of the village take pride in keeping their surroundings clean, a daily habit. Drainage water is redirected for agricultural use, for which a small tax is

levied for the service. Additionally, the village has a program that provides ₹51,000 to families to support their daughters' weddings, celebrate the birth of a daughter, and promote gender equality. With the installation of an additional solar system for non-household purposes, such as water supply and the gram panchayat office, the

village's solar capacity has increased to 109 kilowatts. A one-kilowatt solar unit generates approximately 120 units of electricity per month, and the village will generate around 13,000 units of electricity per month. As a result, the village has become 100% self-sufficient in terms of electricity.

Table No. 1. Villagers Satisfied by Development Activities in Manyachiwadi

Sr.No.	Development Activities	Percentage of Satisfied Villagers
1	Water Conservation and Agricultural Improvement	98
2	Agriculture and Economic Progress	95
3	Education and Social Development	99
4	Health and Sanitation	98
5	Solar Projects and Waste Management	100

Fig no. 2. Villagers Satisfied by Development Activities in Manyachiwadi

Education and Social Development:

The villagers also collectively focused on the education of their children. Schools and libraries were established in the village, providing children with access to quality education and increasing their future prospects. From a social development perspective, the village has self-help groups for women and organizes various social programs. 99 respondents have responded on education and social development. 99% of the people feel that work has been done in this regard.

Health and Sanitation:

Manyachiwadi has also emphasized health and sanitation. The village has implemented various initiatives to maintain cleanliness, including the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan. The villagers have improved public toilets, roads, and water supply systems, creating a healthy environment in the village. 98 respondents have responded on health and sanitation. 98% of the people feel that work has been done in this regard.

When Mahatma Gandhi's conflict-free village campaign was started, Manyachiwadi won in the very first year and made the village conflict-free. The village has maintained the tradition of unopposed elections at the local level. The five-yearly elections of the Gram Panchayat have also been held unopposed. Keeping a policy of cleanliness and other activities as a part of the cleanliness campaign, Manyachiwadi has preserved cleanliness as a culture.

Manyachiwadi a village in Patan tehsil of Maharashtra has created its own identity due to innovative initiatives like vermicomposting projects in every house, buffaloes in every house, toilets in every house, and internet facilities from the first grade in primary schools.

Observations:

1. Initially, there were many problems in the village such as lack of water, low agricultural income and lack of education.
2. Manyachiwadi village has developed in terms of water conservation and agricultural reforms.
3. Manyachiwadi village has made agricultural and economic progress through various schemes and initiatives.
4. The village has made tremendous progress in terms of education and social development.
5. A large number of people have become aware of health and cleanliness in the village.
6. Along with energy conservation, the village has tried to get rid of load shedding.
7. Manyachiwadi village has moved towards becoming the first solar village in the country in a short period of time.

Conclusion:

Manyachiwadi village has overcome various challenges and become a self-sufficient community and has achieved success in various areas like solar power, water conservation, agriculture, education, health, and sanitation. The village has also implemented innovative initiatives like vermicomposting, biogas, and e-learning through collective efforts of villagers in Manyachiwadi. Village has become an ideal village through implementing innovative initiatives and collective efforts. Manyachiwadi village is considered an

excellent example of rural development not only in Maharashtra but also in the whole of India. The unity and hard work of the villagers have proven that any difficulty can be overcome with the right direction and efforts. Due to all these efforts Manyachiwadi village is at the forefront in all matters.

References:

1. Census of India 2011. (2014). *Census of India Website: Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India*. <https://Censusindia.Gov.in/2011>. <https://censusindia.gov.in/>
2. Socio-Economic Review and Statistical Abstract of Satara, (2011) and (2017): Department of Semantic and Statistics, Government of Maharashtra, Mumbai.
3. Mahades, Maharashtra.gov.in (2012): <http://www.mahades.maharashtra.gov.in>
4. <https://villageinfo.in/maharashtra/satara/patan/manyachiwadi.html>
5. <http://www.onefivenine.com/india/villages/Satara/Patan/Manyachiwadi>
6. <https://www.mahadiscom.in/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Vidyut-Warta-Sep-2024.pdf>
7. <https://sarkarigr.in>
8. <https://www.youtube.com>
9. <https://www.tarunbharat.net>
10. <https://www.lokmat.com/satara>
11. <https://energy.vikaspedia.in>
12. <https://www.pressalert.in/maharashtra>